

PSEUDOALLERGY: ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS AND MODERN METHODS OF PHARMACOTHERAPY

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Abstract

In the modern world, allergies rank among the most common adverse reactions to medications and food products. However, certain reactions occur without the formation of antibodies, yet they present with similar clinical symptoms. This phenomenon is known as "pseudoallergy" or non-allergic anaphylaxis. Like true allergies, pseudoallergies involve various subtypes and activation mechanisms. Regardless of the underlying pathway, these reactions ultimately result in the release of mediators, particularly histamine. This article examines the pathomechanisms of pseudoallergies and highlights current approaches to their pharmacological management.

Keywords: pseudoallergy, complement, histamine, mast cells, arachidonic acid, leukotrienes, prostaglandins.

1. Introduction

Allergy (Greek: allos, other + ergon, Greek: action) is a qualitatively changed reaction of the body to the action of substances of an antigenic or hapten nature, which is associated with the restructuring of the immune system and is accompanied by a disorder of the function of target organs [2, p. 966].

Pseudoallergy (pseudo - Greek: false) is the development of a pathological process identical to an allergic reaction in terms of clinical manifestations, but without an immunological stage (the substance that caused the reaction is not an allergen, and the reaction occurs without the production of antibodies) [3, p. 94].

In contrast to true allergy, pseudoallergy does not require sensitization, i.e., the reaction occurs at the first entry of the substance into the body [29].

Pseudoallergy has similar and almost identical symptoms to true allergy (Table 1.), among which the most dangerous are: cardiogenic shock, myocardial infarction, ventricular blockade.

Another difference is the rate of development of symptoms: at the beginning of the development of a pseudoallergic reaction, symptoms appear quickly and their severity decreases over time, instead of increasing, as in the case of a true allergy [20, p. 163].

In the pathogenesis of pseudoallergic reactions, mechanisms related to changes in the exchange of histamine and biogenic amines, activation of the complement system and disturbance of fatty acid metabolism and disturbance of the balance between lipid mediators are distinguished [5, p. 56; 6, p. 104].

Table 1

Symptoms of pseudoallergy [20]

Cardiovascular	Broncho-pulmonary	Hematological	Skin	Gastro-intestinal	Neuro-psycho-somatic	Systemic
Angioedema	Apnea					
Arrhythmia	Bronchospasm		Cyanosis		Back pain	
Cardiogenic shock	Cough	Granulocytopenia	Erythema	Bloating	Chest pain	Chills
Edema	Dyspnea	Leukopenia	Flushing	Cramping	Chest tightness	Sweating
Hypertension	Hoarseness	Lymphopenia	Nasal congestion	Diarrhea	Confusion	Feeling of warmth
Hypotension	Hyperventilation	Leukocytosis	Rash	Metallic taste	The feeling of imminent death	Fever
Hypoxia	Laryngospasm	Granulocytosis	Rhinitis	Nausea	Fear	Loss of consciousness
Myocardial infarction	Respiratory distress	Thrombocytopenia	Swelling	Vomit	Headache	
Ventricular blockade	Sneeze		Tearing		Panic	
	Stridor		Urticaria			

1. Historical information

About 100 years ago, during the industrialization of Europe and America, antitoxic serums were introduced into medical practice, which in turn caused strange reactions that were difficult to explain. Few could suspect the influence of the immune system on these disorders. Then the Viennese pediatrician Clemens von Pirke became interested in this problem and on April 2, 1903, in collaboration with Bel Schick, wrote a preliminary report of his theory entitled "On the theory of infectious diseases" ("Zur Theorie der Infektionskrankheiten").

On June 25, 1903, the French immunologist Nicolas Artus conducted an experiment in which he successively injected horse serum subcutaneously into rabbits. He established that with each introduction of a foreign protein (which was non-toxic), the specific sensitivity to it increased.

This experiment contributed to the development of Pirke's idea, then it became clear that the existing concept of immunity at that time was inadequate. So, in 1906, Pirke published an article under the title "Allergy" ("Allergie"). In 1911, he published a monograph in which he clarified that the term allergy should be used for immunological reactions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Diagram of von Pirke's initial idea of allergy. According to which, upon contact of the human body with an antigen, there is a change in reactivity. This change can cause a "protective" response that renders the person insensitive to the antigen (immunity) or a "harmful" response that causes symptoms

Pirke's theory has been criticized a lot. The French immunologist Charles Richet believed that it is more appropriate to use the term "anaphylaxis" (from the opposite of "phylaxis" - protection), which he introduced during the study of the individual sensitivity of dogs to toxins.

In 1913, when Richet received the Nobel Prize for the study of anaphylaxis, the term "allergy" began to attract the attention of scientists. As a result, the topic of allergy became very popular, but this recognition caused a "retribution" - the original meaning of the word "allergy" was misunderstood and distorted. Thus, until the middle of the 20th century, this term replaced the concept of anaphylaxis, which was attributed to the properties of immunity, and not to changes in immune reactivity.

Until the 1960s, there were no significant changes in the understanding of the term "allergy". In 1963, Robin Coombs and Philip Jell drew attention to this and in their book "Clinical Aspects of Immunology" provided a new classification of various types of hypersensitivity, distinguishing 4 main types of allergic reactions [1, p. 966]:

Type I - reactive (anaphylactic) - is associated with the formation of highly active antibodies with the participation of IgE. (anaphylactic shock, Quincke's edema)

Type II - cytotoxic - is associated with the formation of antibodies (IgG and IgM) against antigens that are on the surface of the cell or are its components, which leads to the activation of the complement system and the occurrence of complement-dependent cytotoxicity. (hemolytic anemia)

Type III - immune complex - associated with the formation of freely circulating immune complexes in the blood and intercellular fluid with the participation of IgM and IgG, which leads to the activation of the

complement system and the formation of microprecipitates on the vessel walls (Artus phenomenon)

Type IV - delayed - is associated with the formation of sensitized T-lymphocytes (T-effectors), which produce a number of mediators - lymphokines (allergic contact dermatitis, transplant rejection) [2, p. 94].

In the 1970s, the study of histamine release under the influence of dextran or codeine led to the formation of the concept of "pseudoallergy" by the Hungarian immunologist Paul Kahlo. According to this concept, pseudoallergic reactions occur upon first contact with the pathogen (i.e., without prior sensitization) and are clinically very similar to allergic reactions (mainly type I), but occur without the formation of an antigen-antibody complex.

In 2001, the European Academy of Allergology and Clinical Immunology (EAACI) proposed the use of the term "non-allergic anaphylaxis" instead of "pseudoallergic reaction", but the terms are still used interchangeably.

Also in 2001, EAACI made an attempt to standardize the allergological nomenclature. The declaration was supported by the World Organization of Allergology and was revised in 2004 [1, p. 966].

In 2023, EAACI described a novel classification of allergy. According to this classification, there are following mechanisms of allergy:

- Inflammation/immune system-driven mechanisms:
 - Type I (immediate; IgE-depend);
 - Type II (cytotoxic; Complement-depend cytotoxicity, via IgM and IgG);
 - Type III (immune complexes; via IgM and IgG);
- Cell-mediated mechanisms:
 - Type IVa (T1; Innate immune cells (ILC) 1, Th1, Tc1);

- Type IVb (T2; ILC 2, Th2, Tc2);
- Type IVc (T3; ILC 3, Th17, Tc17);
- Tissue-driven mechanisms:
 - Type V (epithelial, associated with resident cells changes, has epigenetic impact);
 - Type VI (metabolic, through metabolic-induced immune dysregulation);
 - Direct response to chemicals;
 - Type VII (direct cellular and inflammatory response to chemical substances) [61, p. 2851].

2. Mechanisms of pseudoallergy

There are 3 mechanisms in the pathogenesis of pseudoallergic reactions:

- Violation of histamine metabolism;
- Activation of the complement system;
- Violation of arachidonic acid metabolism [5, p. 56; 6, p. 104; 7, p. 11].

4. Reactions related to the exchange of histamine

Reactions related to histamine metabolism are the most common and include 4 subtypes:

- Increased release of histamine;
- Consumption of products containing biogenic amines (food);
- Reduction of histamine inactivation;
- Dysbacteriosis [5, p. 56; 7, p. 11].

4.1. Increased release of histamine

Increased release is characteristic of children in the first years of life and is considered a variation of the norm; for adults and older children, it is considered a pathological process [60, p. 185].

The main mechanism of development of this subtype is the release of histamine from mast cells or tissue basophils under the influence of non-immunological factors. It most often occurs in inflammatory processes of the gastrointestinal tract, when conditions are created for the interaction of unprocessed food histamine liberators with mast cells of the submucosal layer of the walls of the gastrointestinal tract. An increase in the concentration of histamine can occur in several ways [5, p. 56; 7, p. 11].

4.1.1 Degranulation of mast cells

In the first case, etiological factors are able to directly affect the dangerous cells and cause their destruction, which is accompanied by the release of allergy mediators. Such factors are defined as non-selective, cytotoxic.

Among the physical factors, high temperature, ionizing and ultraviolet radiation have a pronounced cytotoxic effect; among chemicals - detergents, strong acids and alkalis, organic solvents and quinine.

In the second case, etiological factors cause degranulation of basophils through receptors on the surface of these cells. Such factors are defined as selective, non-cytotoxic [5, p. 56].

These factors include MRGPRX2 (MAS-related G-protein coupled receptor member X2) receptor agonists [8]:

- polymeric amines;
- antibiotics (polymyxin B, vancomycin);
- muscle relaxants (pancuronium, tubocurarine, rocuronium, atracurium);
- radiopaque agents;

- bee venom;
- narcotic analgesics (codeine, morphine, meperidine, fentanyl, hydrocodone, oxycodone) [6, p. 104; 8].

In addition to the above drugs, the following can increase the concentration of histamine:

- antibiotics (D-cycloserine, pentamidine, chloroquine);
- antihypertensive drugs (dobutamine);
- antihypertensive drugs (verapamil, alprenolol);
- diuretics (amiloride);
- local anesthetics (mesocaine, procaine, marcaine, prilocaine);
- anesthetics (barbiturates, thiopental) [4, p. 498].

4.1.2. Systemic mastocytosis

Systemic mastocytosis is a disease characterized by the proliferation of mast cells and their infiltration of the skin and internal organs.

It is characterized by excessive release of mediators, which occurs under the influence of external factors or due to the activation of mast cells.

In many cases, it is caused by a mutation in the D816V gene, which encodes the stem cell factor receptor (c-kit), which is present on mast cells. As a result of this, autophosphorylation occurs, which causes uncontrolled hyperproduction of mast cells [50].

4.1.3. Mast cell activation syndrome

Mast cell activation syndrome is characterized by increased and inadequate activation of mast cells with subsequent release of mediators, but without proliferation of mast cells. Clinical manifestations are similar to systemic mastocytosis.

This disease is based on a low threshold for degranulation of mast cells. The genetic basis has not been proven [50].

4.2. Alimentary way of increasing the concentration of histamine.

The alimentary way of increasing histamine is associated with the use of products that contain histamine and other biogenic amines (tyramine, phenylethylamine) or that can cause an increase in the concentration of histamine in the body. This phenomenon is called "histamine intolerance", which is caused by the inability of the body to inactivate the excess amount of histamine that comes with food.

Products rich in histamine include tomatoes, eggplants, spinach, fish, as well as meat that is stored for a long time; products that contain viable yeast (fresh bread, sourdough), as well as fermented foods (cheeses, sausages, sauerkraut, beer, wine).

Natural histamine liberators include pineapple, banana, citrus fruits, cocoa, strawberries, nuts, papaya, licorice, egg white.

Artificial histamine liberators include various food additives: dyes, preservatives, stabilizers, flavorings [4, p. 498; 5, p. 56].

4.3. Reduction of histamine inactivation.

Reduced inactivation of histamine is associated with a violation of the ways of its neutralization in the body, namely:

- Reduction of binding of free histamine;
- Decreased activity of diamine oxidase;
- Decreased methylation during the studyhistamine N-methyltransferase.

4.3.1. Reduced histamine binding.

Reduced histaminopexy is associated with a decrease in the binding activity of the protein histaminepexin, which binds free histamine in the blood. This phenomenon develops in conditions of intoxication of the body, when the specified protein is involved in the neutralization of toxic products [7, p. 11].

4.3.2. Decreased activity of diamine oxidase.

Diamine oxidase (DAO) is a copper-containing enzyme of the class of oxyreductases, the substrate of

Figure 2. Reaction of histamine oxidation by diamine oxidase.

The oxidation products lack mediator activity and are excreted by the kidneys.

A genetic defect of diamine oxidase can be caused by a mutation in the AOC1 gene, which encodes this protein in the human body [9, p. 63]. A decrease in DAO activity may be associated with defects or inflammation of the intestinal mucosa, in chronic renal failure, viral hepatitis, and chronic urticaria [4, p. 498].

Also, a decrease in activity can be observed against the background of the use of drugs that can inhibit DAO. These drugs include:

- antiarrhythmic drugs (verapamil, propafenone);
- antibiotics (cefuroxime, cefotiam, clavulanic acid, doxycycline, isoniazid, framycetin, metronidazole [11, p. 589], chloroquine);
- antidepressants and antipsychotics (amitriptyline, diazepam, MAO inhibitors, haloperidol);
- antihypertensive drugs (hydralazine);
- antiemetics (metoclopramide);
- diuretics (furosemide);
- bronchodilators (aminophylline, theophylline);

which is diamines, in particular histamine, putrescine and cadaverine, as well as polyamines. This enzyme is present in many tissues, particularly in the kidney, intestinal mucosa and placenta, which have the highest content, but in the central nervous system, this enzyme is absent. In the intestines, diamine oxidase plays a leading role in the detoxification of food diamines, in particular exogenous yeastmine (Figure 2).

- muscle relaxants (tubocurarine, alcuronium, pancuronium) [10, p. 9810];

- antihistamines (promethazine, cimetidine).

Among the food sources of DAO inhibitors, alcoholic beverages can be singled out.

A decrease in the amount of the enzyme may be associated with a deficiency of vitamins B6 and C and trace elements Cu and Zn.

Deficiency of vitamin B6 can be caused by the use of drugs that show antagonism in relation to pyridoxine. These drugs include:

- antihypertensive agent (hydralazine);
- antibiotics (D-cyclosporin, isoniazid);
- hormonal contraceptives (contain estrogens) [9, p. 63].

4.3.3. Decreased activity of histamine N-methyltransferase

The third mechanism is associated with the reduction of histamine methylation by histamine N-methyltransferase, an enzyme of the transferase class, which catalyzes the transfer of the methyl radical from S-adenosyl-L-methionine to the imidazole ring of histamine (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The methylation reaction of histamine with S-adenosyl-L-methionine with the formation of N-methylhistamine and S-adenosyl-L-homocysteine by histamine N-methyltransferase

The content of this enzyme prevails in the central nervous system, where it is the only way to inactivate histamine, and its content in tissues is lower and inferior to the content of DAO [12].

A decrease in the activity of histamine N-methyltransferase can occur against the background of a defect in the HNMT gene encoding this enzyme [15].

Among the drugs capable of inhibiting histamine N-methyltransferase:

- antidepressants (MAO inhibitors - pargyline, clorgyline, deprenyl (selegiline));
- antitumor drugs (dihydrofolate reductase inhibitors - ethoprime, methoprime);
- antimalarials (chloroquine, amodiaquine, quinacrine);

- anticholinesterase agents of central action (tacrine) [14, p. 334].

4.4. Dysbacteriosis

Disturbances in the intestinal microflora can cause an increase in the level of histamine.

Normally, bacteria of the *Bifidobacteriaceae* family, which are obligate anaerobes, antagonize bacteria of the *Proteobacteria* type.

In patients with reduced DAO activity, there is an increased number of bacteria of the type *Proteobacteria*, which are able to form histamine as a result of the histidine decarboxylation reaction under the action of L-histidine decarboxylase (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The reaction of histamine formation from histidine under the action of L-histidine decarboxylase.

A number of species that are considered to be potentially probiotic are also capable of producing significant amounts of histamine and other biogenic amines,

such as *Lactobacillus saerimneri* 30a and *Limosilactobacillus reuteri* DSM 17938 (Table 2) [49, p. 2228].

Table 2

Bacteria capable of producing histamine [49]

<i>Acinetobacter spp.</i>	<i>Chryseobacterium spp.</i>	<i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i>
<i>Alcaligenes faecalis</i>	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	<i>Proteus spp.</i>
<i>Arizona spp.</i>	<i>Kluyver spp.</i>	<i>Providencia spp.</i>
<i>Cedecea spp.</i>	<i>Morganella morganii</i>	<i>Serratia spp.</i>
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i> <i>Citrobacter braakii</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus casei</i> <i>Lacticaseibacillus paracasei</i> <i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>	<i>Pseudomonas putida</i> <i>Pseudomonas lundensis</i> <i>Pseudomonas stutzeri</i>
<i>Edwardsiella spp.</i>	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	<i>Psychrobacter spp.</i>
<i>Enterococcus casseliflavus</i> <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i> <i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	<i>Lactobacillus curvatus</i> <i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i> <i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	<i>Raoultella planticola</i> <i>Raoultella ornithinolytica</i>
<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>	<i>Lactococcus lactis ssp. lactis</i>	<i>Salmonella enterica ssp. arizona</i>
<i>Escherichia coli</i> <i>Escherichia fergusonii</i>	<i>Latilactobacillus spp.</i> <i>Lentilactobacillus buchneri</i> <i>Lentilactobacillus hilgardii</i> <i>Lentilactobacillus parabuchneri</i>	<i>Providencia heimbachae</i>
<i>Halomonas spp.</i>	<i>Leuconostoc spp.</i>	<i>Sphingobacterium spp.</i>
<i>Hafnia alvei</i> <i>Hafnia paralvei</i>	<i>Limosilactobacillus reuteri</i> <i>Limosilactobacillus vaginalis</i>	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>
	<i>Microbacterium foliorum</i>	<i>Tetragenococcus halophilus</i>

5. Reactions are associated with the activation of the complement system

The basis of the second mechanism of pseudoallergy is an inadequate reaction of complement, which is associated with the strengthening or inclusion of various ways of its activation.

Soluble proteins of the complement system are synthesized by the liver and circulate in the blood mainly in the form of inactive pro-enzymes, which become active as a result of cleavage by proteases [30, p. 579].

The result of complement activation is the formation of anaphylatoxins C3a, C4a, C5a and mem-

brane attack complex (C5b-9), which provoke degranulation of mast cells and the release of allergy mediators [16].

5.1. Ways of complement activation

In the human body, the complement system can be activated in 3 different ways: classical (antigen-antibody complex), alternative (accelerated breakdown of the C3 component) or lectin (through lectin binding).

Each path has its own specific activators, but each path ends with the formation of anaphylatoxins and a membrane attack complex (Figure 5) [6, p. 104; 30, p. 579].

Figure 5. Complement cascade.

5.1.1 The classical way.

The classical pathway of activation depends on antibodies, and is activated when the antibody binds to the antigen. Among antibodies, only IgM and IgG are able to activate the complement system.

The formed antigen-antibody complex connects with the C1q component of complement, which leads to the activation of the C1-complex and the start of the complement cascade [6, p. 104; 19, p. 317].

5.1.2 Alternative path

An alternative way is determined by the ability of some substances (C-reactive protein, viral proteins, polyanions, β -amyloid and others) to activate the complement system in a non-immunological way.

The basis of this mechanism is the spontaneous hydrolysis of the C3 component to form its hydrolyzate C3(H₂O), which is exposed to the action of proteases B and D. The product of their reaction C3(H₂O)Bb, under the action of C3-convertase, is further included in the cascade of reactions, as in the classical pathway.

Under normal conditions, healthy cells have a number of mechanisms that prevent spontaneous hydrolysis of C3 and unwanted activation of the complement system [19, p. 317].

5.1.3. Lectin pathway

Trigger mechanisms in the lectin pathway of complement activation are mannose-binding lectin (MBL) and ficolins, which recognize carbohydrate sequences on the surface of microorganisms.

Each such molecule binds to MBL-associated serine protease (MASP), which has structural similarity to C1s or C1r fragments of complement. MASP-2 cuts C4 and C2 components into C4a and C2a fragments, respectively, which, under the action of C3-convertase, are included in the complement cascade, similar to the classical and alternative pathways [21, p. 785].

5.2. Inadequate complement response

5.2.1. Reinforcement of the classic way

Inadequate enhancement of the classical pathway of complement activation occurs in patients with hereditary angioedema (HANE) [5]. This disease is caused by a mutation in the SERPING1 gene, which encodes C1-esterase inhibitor (C1-INH). In this case, a defective C1-inhibitor with lower activity (C1-INH-HAE) is synthesized in the human body.

There are 2 types of this disease. Mutations causing the first type are spread throughout the gene and provoke precisely the deficiency of C1-INH. The second type is caused by mutations located in the loop of the reactive center of the specified protein and provoke dysfunction of this enzyme.

There are known forms of hereditary angioedema, which is observed against the background of normal level and activity of C1-INH (there is no mutation in the SERPING1 gene), in which case nC1-INH-HAE (SAN with normal C1-inhibitor) is formed.

The appearance of nC1-INH-HAE is caused by a mutation in one of 6 genes (Table 3) [18, p. 2023].

Table 3

Genes which causes nC1-INH-HAE [18]

Gene name	What coding
F12	Factor XII
PLG	Plasminogen
ANGPT1	Angioprotein 1
KNG1	Kininogen 1
MYOF	Myofelin
HS3ST6	Heparan sulfate glucosamine 3-O-sulfoesterase 6

5.2.2 Non-immunological activation of the complement system.

Among the drugs that can activate the complement system are: liposomal drugs, drugs in micellar solvents,

antibodies, radiocontrast agents; various enzymes, proteins, peptides, etc. (Table 4) [20, p. 163].

Table 4

Medicines capable of activating the complement system and causing pseudoallergy [20]

Liposomal drugs	Micelle-solubilized drugs	Antibodies	PEGylated protein	Contrast media	Enzymes, proteins, peptides	Miscellaneous
Abelcet AmBisome Amphotec Amphocyl DaunoX-ome Doxil, Caelyx Myocet Visudyne	Cyclosporine Elitec Etoposide Fasturec Taxol Taxotere Vumo	Avastin Campath Erbix Herceptin Infliximab Muronomab Mylotarg Remicade Rituxan Vertibix Xolair	Adagen Neulasta Oncaspar Pegaspargas	Diatrizoat Iodipamide Iodixanol Iohexol Iopamidol Iopromide Iothalamate Ioversol Ioxaglate Ioxilan Magnevist Metrizamide SonoVue	Abbokinase ACH Actimmune Activase Aldurazyme Avonex Fasturtec Neulasta Neupogen Plenaxis protamine Urokinase Zevalin	ACE Inhibitors AR blockets Aspirin Cancidas Copaxone Corticosteroids Cyprofloxacin Eloxatin Intralipid Opiates Salicilates Vancomycin

5.2.2.1. Radiocontrast means.

Radiocontrast agents have a complex effect on the activation of the complement system in an alternative way mainly through physical phenomena (charge, hydrophilicity, osmotic pressure) and are able to provoke hydrolysis of the C3 component, inhibit factors H and I, and have a direct effect on the thioester bonds of C3 and C4 components [17, p. 106].

5.2.2.2. Liposomal preparations.

Liposomal drugs (Doxil, etc.) are able to activate the complement system through classical and alternative pathways (the classical pathway of activation prevails). Activation of complement by the classical way in this case may be caused by the binding of the C1q component or C-reactive protein by the phospholipid bilayer.

The formation of liposomal-reactive immunoglobulins can be a powerful trigger or enhancer of the complement cascade, but their presence is not a prerequisite for complement activation by the classical pathway.

Also, Doxil is able to activate factor B and significantly increase the level of the Bb component of complement, which indicates the activation or enhancement of the alternative pathway of complement.

5.2.2.3. Amphiphilic emulsifiers

Solvents containing amphiphilic emulsifiers belong to another group of drugs capable of non-immunologically activating complement. These include semi-synthetic Cremofor El and synthetic copolymers, such as poloxamer 188 [17, p. 106; 20, p. 163].

Cremofor El is a nonionic detergent, a complex mixture of unmodified castor oil, polyethylene glycol, amphiphilic polyethoxylated glycerols, polyethoxylated fatty acids and polyethoxylated glycerol esters. It is used as a solvent for drugs that are poorly soluble in water (taxol, cyclosporine, steroids, vitamins A, D, E, K).

Being physiologically inert, this solvent is able to activate the complement system mainly in an alternative way, binding the C3 component with a hydrophilic

surface without the formation of immune complexes. [17, p. 106; 20, p. 163; 22].

Poloxamer is a series of closely interconnected blocks of copolymers of ethylene oxide and propylene oxide. Poloxamer 188 as an emulsifier is part of intravenous preparations in the form of fat emulsions, as well as perfluorocarbon artificial blood substitutes. As an active pharmaceutical component, it is used to treat constipation, kidney stone disease, and to clean the wound surface.

Poloxamer 188 is able to activate the complement system in an alternative way and significantly increase the level of the C5b-9 component due to the binding of the hydrophilic sections of the C3 component with the subsequent launch of the complement cascade [17, p. 106; 23].

5.2.2.4. Polysaccharides

Sugars, glycans and sugar polymers are able to activate the complement system mainly through the lectin and alternative pathways, but the classical pathway through the binding of sugars to the C1q component is also possible [24, p. 1031].

Sugars capable of affecting the complement system in this way include:

- Dextran is a component of blood and plasma substitutes [25].

- Chitosan is a component of mucoadhesive dosage forms and dosage forms with rapid release of the active pharmaceutical ingredient [26].

Polysaccharides capable of inhibiting the complement system include heparin [24, p. 1031].

5.2.2.5. Carbon nanotubes

Carbon nanotubes are cylindrical structures consisting of one or more graphite layers bent into a tube with a hexagonal arrangement of carbon atoms. They are divided into single-walled (SWCNTs), double-walled (DWCNTs) and multi-walled (MWCNTs). In medicine, they are used as drug carriers [27]. Carbon nanotubes are able to activate complement systems in 3 different ways. (Table 5) [24, p. 1031].

Table 5

Classification of carbon nanotubes and their influence on the activation of the complement system [24]

Classical pathway	Alternative pathway	Lectin pathway
<p>SWCNTs: Non-functionalized Iron filled Glycolipid-functionalized RNA-wrapped</p>	<p>SWCNTs: Non-functionalized (little)</p>	<p>SWCNTs: PEGylated PEG-Phospholipid-coated Glycolipid-functionalized</p>
<p>DWCNTs: Non-functionalized Human fibrinogen-coated Tween 20-coated</p>	<p>DWCNTs: Non-functionalized</p>	
<p>MWCNTs: Non-functionalized L-alanine-functionalized Nylon 6-functionalized Ironfilled Glycolipid-functionalized</p>	<p>MWCNTs: L-alanine-functionalized Nylon 6-functionalized</p>	

6. Reactions associated with disturbance of arachidonic acid metabolism

The third mechanism of pseudoallergy is related to a violation of the metabolism of fatty acids, in particular arachidonic acid [5, p. 56]. The main manifestation of such reactions is aspirin-induced asthma.

Aspirin-induced asthma is a syndrome that develops due to the use of aspirin or other nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (cyclooxygenase (COX) inhibitors). This syndrome is characterized by eosinophilic rhinosinusitis, nasal polyposis, sensitivity to aspirin and asthma, but without the formation of antibodies [32, p. 2417; 33, p. 913].

This mechanism of pseudoallergy is based on a violation of the balance of the cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase pathways of arachidonic acid oxidation towards the predominant formation of leukotrienes [33, p. 913].

6.1. Ways of metabolism of arachidonic acid

Normally, arachidonic acid released from phospholipids under the action of phospholipase A2 with the participation of COX forms prostaglandins (PG), and under the action of 5-lipoxygenase - leukotrienes (LT) (Figure 6) [35].

Figure 6. Metabolic pathways of arachidonic acid through the enzymatic actions of COX-1/COX-2 and 5-LOX.

6.1.1. Synthesis of prostaglandins. Cyclooxygenases 1 and 2

COX-1 and COX-2 are isoenzymes responsible for the development of inflammation.

COX-1 is present in tissues and participates in the maintenance of homeostasis (affects gastric mucosa, renal circulation and platelet aggregation).

COX-2 is inducible and directly involved in the development of inflammation. This enzyme is activated

under the influence of external factors (for example, lipopolysaccharide endotoxins) [34, p. 109].

COX-3 is the third isoform responsible for the synthesis of prostaglandins in the central nervous system. This form of COX is not involved in the development of inflammation, but plays a role in the development of fever and pain [38, p. 23].

Among prostaglandins involved in the pathophysiology of aspirin-induced asthma, the following play significant roles:

- PGE₂, which inhibits 5-lipoxygenase activity and reduces LT synthesis [31, p. 259];
- PGD₂, which contributes the development of inflammation in the respiratory tract;
- PGI₂, which prevents the activation of innate immune cells type 2 [46, p. 755];
- 9 α , 11-F₂, which induces bronchoconstriction [36, p. 681].

PGD₂ derivatives - thromboxanes A₂ and B₂ also exhibit bronchoconstrictor properties [41, p. 111].

6.1.2. Synthesis of leukotrienes. Lipoxygenases

At least 6 different lipoxygenases are known in the human body, but of this class of enzymes, 5-lipoxygenase (arachidonate: 5-O-oxygenase) (5-LOX) is associated with human diseases.

This enzyme catalyzes the oxidation reaction of arachidonic acid into 5-hydroxyperoxyeicosatetraenoic

acid (5-HPETE), an intermediate compound in the synthesis of leukotrienes [39, p. 5866-5898] and a key compound in the synthesis of LTA₄. This unstable leukotriene is metabolized through LTA₄ hydrolase to LTB₄, or conjugated through LTC₄ synthase to LTC₄ [40, p. 1].

Among LTs, the leading role in the pathogenesis of aspirin asthma is played by cystenyl LTs (cys-LTs) - LTC₄, LTD₄, LTE₄ [36, p. 681].

6.2. Pathogenesis of aspirin-induced asthma

The basis of the pathogenesis of aspirin asthma is the persistent activation of eosinophils due to the increased production of leukotrienes and the development of type 2 inflammation in the respiratory tract.

The key inflammatory cells in this inflammation are mast cells and eosinophils, which closely interact with other inflammatory and structural cells, including basophils, platelets, and epithelial cells (Table 6.) [42, p. 1147].

Table 6

Mechanisms of aspirin-mediated reactions

Cells	Mediators
- Mast cells Activation during the reaction and release of mediators [43].	- Cys - LT - rapid increase in level during the reaction. They cause the manifestation of the reaction, increase the severity of the course [42].
- Eosinophils/basophils Significant influx into respiratory system tissues during the reaction [36].	- PG D ₂ thromboxanes A ₂ and B ₂ - increased levels. It provokes bronchoconstriction, increases the severity of the reaction [42, 47].
- Platelets Increased activation, increased platelet - leukocyte adhesion, which contributes to the production of cis -LT and PG D ₂ and the manifestation of the reaction [36].	- PGE ₂ – decreased level. Normally, it prevents the degranulation of fatty cells [43].
- Epithelial cells Activated by cis - LT, they produce interleukins (ILs) [45].	- PG I ₂ – level decrease. Normally, it prevents inactivation of innate type 2 lymphoid cells [46].
- Innate immune cells type 2. Activation during the reaction. Produce cytokines. Cause the manifestation of the reaction [45].	- Histamine and tryptase – increased during reactions due to mast cell degranulation . They cause the manifestation of the reaction, increase the severity of the course [36] .

6.2.1 Mast cells

The activation of mast cells has a significant impact on the manifestations of aspirin asthma. The main activators of mast cells are interleukins (IL): IL-33, IL-25 and IL-9 [46]. Under normal conditions, PGE₂, interacting with EP₂ and EP₄ receptors, prevents their activation, however, under conditions of lack of this PG, the ability of mast cells to degranulate increases significantly. Also, the increased activation of mast cells can be caused by an increase in the concentration of Ca²⁺ ions due to an increase in the level of cys-LTs [43, p. 463].

Degranulation of mast cells leads to the release of inflammatory mediators, including PGD₂, however mast cells are not the only source of PGD₂ [44].

6.2.2 Innate immune cells type 2

PGD₂ and cys-LT stimulate innate lymphoid cells of type 2 by interacting with receptors DP₂ (agonist - PGD₂), CysLT_{1R} and CysLT_{2R} (agonists - LTC₄ and LTD₄, less active - LTE₄), P_{2Y}12 and GPR₉₉ (agonist - LTE₄).

Type 2 innate immune cells produce large amounts of IL-4, IL-5, and IL-13. IL-5 provokes the development of eosinophilia, while IL-4 and IL-13, together with cys-LTs and PGD₂, contribute to the development of inflammation in the upper and lower respiratory tract, mucus production, and bronchoconstriction [45, p. 7].

6.2.3. Eosinophils

The number of eosinophils in aspirin asthma in the peripheral blood increases. There is migration of eosinophils into the tissues of the respiratory tract, activation and prolongation of the action of interleukin-5, but unlike eosinophilic inflammation, its concentration does not increase. Activation of eosinophils contributes to the expression of LTC₄ synthase, production of γ -interferon and PGD₂, and sensitivity to NSAIDs, which dose-dependently stimulate the release of these mediators [44].

6.2.4. Platelets

Another source of PGD₂, TXA₂ and cys-LTs are activated platelets after adhesion with leukocytes. Platelet activation occurs under the action of P-selectin

as a result of stimulation of P2Y₁₂ receptors. In addition to the fact that platelets are capable of synthesizing LT, they are able to modulate their synthesis through leukocytes.

Platelets lack 5-LOX, but LTC₄ synthase is sufficient. Neutrophils, in turn, have 5-LOX and are capable of synthesizing excess LTA₄, which is hydrolyzed to LTB₄. When a platelet attaches to a neutrophil, excess LTA₄ is converted to LTC₄ [47, p. 1407].

6.3. Medicinal products that provoke aspirin asthma

Medicines capable of inducing aspirin asthma include NSAIDs capable of inhibiting COX-1.

Non-selective COX inhibitors are poorly tolerated by sensitive patients. These drugs include: ibuprofen, indomethacin, naproxen, fenoprofen, meclofenamate, ketorolac, etololac, diclofenac, ketoprofen, piroxicam, nabumetone, mefenamic acid. Paracetamol in doses below 500 mg is well tolerated.

Drugs that mainly inhibit COX-2 are better tolerated, but in large doses can provoke aspirin-like asthma: meloxicam, nimesulide.

Selective COX-2 inhibitors are well tolerated and do not cause symptoms: etoricoxib, celecoxib, parvcoxib, as well as salsalate and trisalicylate [51, p. 818].

7. Pharmacotherapy of pseudoallergic conditions

Treatment of pseudoallergy is aimed at eliminating its pathochemical and pathophysiological stages.

7.1. Histamine type

7.1.1. Antihistamines

In histamine-type pseudoallergy, the use of antihistamines is not recommended because they selectively block H₁-histamine receptors. This selective blockade can amplify the effects of excess histamine on H₂, H₃, and H₄ histamine receptors. Significant stimulation of these receptors leads to several undesirable effects:

- H₂ receptors: increased gastric juice secretion;
- H₃ receptors: impaired cardiac function and central nervous system depression;
- H₄ receptors: disruptions in hematopoiesis [7, p. 11].

7.1.2. Increased release of histamine

The increased release of histamine can be mitigated through the use of mast cell membrane stabilizers such as ketotifen and sodium cromoglycate [5, p. 56; 7, p. 11].

Degranulation of mast cells can also be inhibited by certain plant-derived compounds that interact with MRGPRX₂ receptors (Table 7). Additionally, several synthetic compounds have demonstrated the ability to reduce MRGPRX₂-mediated degranulation, including aptamer-X35, roxithromycin, suggamadex, lactic acid, sphingomyelin, and dexamethasone [52, p. 2906].

Table 7

Natural compounds that can affect mast cells through receptors MRGPRX₂

Compound name	Class of chemical compounds
Piperine	Alkaloid
Isoliquiritigenin	Flavonoid
Shikonin	Flavonoid
Imperatorin	Furocoumarin
Paeoniflorin	Terpene
Quercetin	Flavonoid
Resveratrol	Polyphenol
Licochalcone A	Halcon
Ostol	Coumarin

7.1.3. Alimentary way

Enzyme preparations can be prescribed to neutralize food histamine liberators, and sorbents can be prescribed to prevent intoxication [7, p. 11].

Patients should also be prescribed a diet excluding food sources of histamine [53, p. 1181].

7.1.4. Decreased DAO activity

The lack of DAO can be partially compensated by the use of special dietary supplements containing exogenous DAO [53] (HistDAO) [54, p. 185].

7.1.5. Dysbacteriosis

In the case of dysbacteriosis, its correction with pro- and eubiotics is necessary. Also effective is the appointment of lactulose, which on the one hand promotes the development of microflora, and on the other - detoxification of the body [7, p. 11].

7.2. Inadequate complement response

7.2.1 Hereditary angioedema

Since hereditary angioedema is a genetic disease, there is no etiotropic therapy. The treatment strategy is aimed at reducing or preventing attacks and reducing mortality.

In the case of angioneurotic disease caused by C1-INH deficiency, it would be appropriate to administer C1-INH obtained from blood plasma of donors (Synraz drug) or recombinant human C1-INH (Rukonest) [55, p. 391], transfusion of freshly frozen donor plasma (containing C1-INH) is possible. [5, p. 56]. In acute cases, Icatibant (Firazir, Shire) can be prescribed - a blocker of B₂-bradykinin receptors [56].

For prevention, patients can use tranexamic acid (synthetic analogue of lysine) and attenuated androgens (danazol or oxandrolone) [55, p. 391].

7.2.2. Non-immunological complement activation

The complement cascade is characterized by the activation of proteolytic systems, therefore, to inhibit it, it will be appropriate to use proteolysis inhibitors - ε-aminocaproic acid or aprotinin [7, p. 11].

The formation of anaphylotoxins can be reduced by inhibiting a number of enzymes at different stages of their formation:

- Compstatin is a C3-convertase inhibitor
- Eculizumab, pexelizumab - monoclonal antibodies against the C5 component.

In addition to formation, it is possible to block their action:

- Anti-C5a – antibody against C5a anaphylatoxin;
- C5aR-inhibitor, neitrazumab - antagonists of C5a anaphylatoxin receptors.

Activation of the lectin pathway can be stopped by inhibiting serine proteases (nafamostat) and factor D (factor D-inhibitor) [19, p. 317].

7.3. Aspirin asthma

7.3.1. Replacement of NSAIDs

The treatment of aspirin-induced asthma involves the replacement of NSAIDs with more selective ones for COX-2 with the complete exclusion of COX-1 inhibitors (including aspirin) [58, p. 41].

7.3.2. Physiological and saline solutions

In case of chronic rhinosinusitis, it is recommended to rinse the nose with a saline solution or use saline sprays. It is useful to use irrigation to clean the nasal mucosa before the administration of glucocorticoids [57, p. 805].

7.3.3. Nasal glucocorticoids

Systemic and local corticosteroids may be used to block eosinophilic infiltration [57, p. 805; 58, p. 41].

Nasal glucocorticoids: budesonide, fluticasone propionate, mometasone furoate, triamcinolone acetonide, beclomethazone dipropionate, and fluticasone furoate are considered first-line drugs for the treatment of chronic rhinosinusitis caused by the use of NSAIDs. These drugs are highly effective in reducing inflammation, polyp formation, and rhinitis symptoms [57, p. 805].

7.3.4. Antileukotriene drugs

Leukotrienes and their synthesis are targets in the therapy of aspirin-induced asthma.

There are 2 ways: inhibition of 5-LOX and reduction of LT synthesis from arachidonic acid and blocking of CysLTR1 and CysLTR2 receptors.

In the first case, the drug zileuton is used, in the second - montelukast and zafirlukast [59], as well as iralukast, pobilukast, pranlukast [37, p. 338].

7.3.5 Aspirin desensitization

Aspirin desensitization is a provocative procedure that begins with the introduction of increasing doses of aspirin from 650 to 1300 mg over a period of 1 to 3 days, which can provoke hypersensitivity reactions.

Desensitization should be carried out in a well-equipped hospital under the supervision of qualified specialists. A two-day aspirin escalation protocol was approved by the EAACI to improve the efficacy and safety of this procedure [42, p. 1147].

Pregnancy is an absolute contraindication for this procedure. Patients at risk of gastric bleeding should be treated with proton pump inhibitors or misoprostol (a synthetic analogue of PGE₂, which is protective for the sputum mucosa) during the procedure [57, p. 805].

7.3.6. Monoclonal antibodies

Among the new drugs, omalizumab is a monoclonal antibody against IgE, dupilumab is a monoclonal antibody against interleukin IL-4 α receptors, mepolizumab, reslizumab and benralizumab are monoclonal antibodies against IL-5 [42, p. 1147].

7.3.6.1. Omalizumab

Omalizumab binds to IgE and prevents their interaction with high-affinity Fc ϵ RI receptors, and also reduces the expression of these receptors on the surfaces of mast cells and basophils, reducing the ability of mast cells to degranulate. Omalizumab reduces the manifestations of asthma and reduces the need for glucocorticoids and short-term β 2-adrenomimetics, and also improves the condition of patients during the course of aspirin desensitization [42, p. 1147].

7.3.6.2. Dupilumab

Dupilumab inhibits signaling from IL4 and IL13. Its use leads to relief of symptoms in the upper and lower respiratory tract [42, p. 1147].

7.3.6.3. IL-5-targeted monoclonal antibodies.

Mepolizumab and reslizumab prevent the binding of IL-5 to eosinophil receptors. Benralizumab blocks IL-5 receptors by binding to the α -subunit of this protein. Inhibition of these receptors prevents the maturation and migration of eosinophils [42, p. 1147].

7.3.6.4. Promising preparations of monoclonal antibodies.

An additional option in the treatment of aspirin asthma may be promising antibodies: CRTH2 (DP2) antagonist of PGD₂ receptors, anti-IL-33 antibody, and P2Y₁₂-receptor antagonists [42, p. 1147].

Conclusions

Thus, pseudoallergy has its own unique mechanisms of development and a large number of trigger substances, among which there are various drugs and components in their composition, separate groups of drugs and food products.

The basis of pseudoallergy can be already acquired diseases (inflammatory processes in the gastrointestinal tract), including genetic ones (hereditary angioedema, systemic mastocytosis), as well as defects in enzyme systems (defects of DAO, HNMT, etc.).

Pseudoallergy has unique approaches to treatment. Thus, all pharmacotherapy is aimed at eliminating the pathochemical and pathophysiological stages, and drugs aimed at the immune system are much less effective. Approaches to treatment, in turn, differ depending on the mechanism of development of pseudoallergy.

Despite some differences in pathogenesis, pseudo- and true allergy according to the classification of Coombs and Gel are similar in terms of target organs and effector mechanisms. Death most often occurs as a result of cardiac disorders: arrhythmia, ventricular blockade, heart attack and cardiac arrest.

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